

Synthesis and Characterization of Some 3-chloro-azetidone-2-ones Compounds of the 2-amino Pyrimidine Compound and Evaluation of their Biological Activity

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Abstract

This work involved the synthesis of some derivatives of 3-chloro-azetidone-2-one, by two steps: The first include amino group of the 2-amino pyrimidine was condensed with different aromatic aldehydes and ketones in the presence of absolute ethanol to give new Schiff bases derivatives [A1 – A5] respectively. The second step, the resulting imines derivatives [A1 – A10] were reacted with chloro acetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine in 1,4-dioxan by pericyclic reaction to give novel 3-chloro-1-(pyrimidin-2-yl)azetidone-2-one derivatives [A₆ – A₁₀] respectively. characterization by using spectroscopic techniques UV/Vis, FT-IR, C.H.N. and ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR of some the prepared compounds using DMSO-d₆ as a solvent, in addition to melting point and determination a purity of TLC, This work consisted a study of biological activity for some prepared compounds against four types of pathogenic bacteria to detect their resistance to anti-biotic, drugs.

Keywords: 2-aminopyrimidine, 3-chloro-azetidone-2-one, 2-Azetidinones

INTRODUCTION:

2-Azetidinones, commonly known as β -lactams, β -lactams ring is a four membered cyclic amide. It is named as such, because the nitrogen atom is attached to the β - carbon relative to the carbonyl.

β -lactam;
 β -Propiolactam;
2-Azacyclobutanone

2-Azetidinone;
Azetidone-2-one;

The first synthetic β -lactam was prepared by Hermann Staudinger in 1907 by reaction of the Schiff base of aniline and benzaldehyde with diphenylketene in a [2+2] cycloaddition^[1]. The chemistry of β -lactams has taken an important place

in organic chemistry since the discovery of Penicillin by Sir Alexander Fleming in 1928 and shortly thereafter Cephalosporin which were both used as successful antibiotics. Even now the research in this area is stimulated because of development of bacterial resistance to widely used antibiotics of this type. There is a need for functionalized β -lactams or for new active principles in β -lactam series^[2]. The 2-azetidone (β -lactams) ring is a common structural feature of a number of broad spectrum β -lactam antibiotics including penicillins I, cephalosporins II, carbapenems III, nocardicin A IV and monobactams which have been widely used as chemotherapeutic agents to treat bacterial infection and microbial diseases^[3, 4]. Azetidones are very important class of compounds possessing wide range of biological activities such as antibacterial^[5], anti-inflammatory^[6], antihyperlipidemic^[7], CNS activity^[8], trypsinase

inhibitory ^[9], human leukocyte elastase inhibitory ^[10], antihyperglycemic ^[11], vasopressin v1a antagonist ^[12], and anticancer activity ^[13], antimicrobial ^[14], pesticidal ^[15], antitumor ^[16], antitubercular ^[17], cytotoxic ^[18], enzyme inhibitors ^[19], elastase inhibitors ^[20] and cholesterol absorption inhibitors

Experimental

Instruments and Chemicals

All melting points are uncorrected and are expressed in degree(⁰C), using melting point SMP3. IR spectra were recorded as KBr disks using shimadzu FT-IR 8400. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded using Varian VnmrJ 400 spectrometer (400 MHz) and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard using DMSO-d₆ as solvent the peaks showed at δ=(2.5-2.4)ppm, ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded using Varian VnmrJ 400 spectrometer (100 MHz) and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard using

DMSO-d₆ as solvent Elemental analysis using Leco CHNS-933 Leco corporation st.Joseph ..

Synthesis Methods

General procedure for synthesis Schiff bases [A₁ – A₅] ^[21] :

The 2-aminopyrimidine (0.01 mole, 0.95 gm) was added to a solution of the different substituted benzaldehydes (0.01 mole) in 40ml of absolute ethanol and two drops of glacial acetic acid were also added to the above mixture. The mixture was refluxed for (15-20 h.) and at the end of the reaction; solvents were partially evaporated then poured into water. The precipitates were collected by filtration , washed with diethylether , dried and recrystallized from the appropriate solvent like ethanol or ethanol-water **Scheme 1**.

Scheme 1

Table (1): physical properties, yield and Rf of schiff base [A₁-A₅].

Comp. No.	Ar	Molecular Formula/ M.Wt g/mol	Color	M.P. (°C)	Yield (%)	Rf Acet. +EtOH
A ₁		C₁₂H₈N₄ 208	Pale yellow	170-172	88	0.83
A ₂		C₁₂H₁₁N₃OS 245	Yellow	152-154	77	0.75
A ₃		C₁₁H₇N₃ Cl₂ 251	Pale brown	170-172	66	0.66
A ₄		C₁₂H₁₁N₃O₂ 229	Yellow	218-220	73	0.70
A ₅		C₁₄H₁₁N₃O 237	Green	212-214	81	0.79

General procedure for synthesis azetidinone analogs [A₆-A₁₀]^[22]:

To a mixture of Schiff bases [A₁-A₅](0.01 mol) in dioxane (10 ml) and triethylamine (3.49 ml, 0.025 mol), was added chloroacetyl chloride (1.99 ml,

0.025 mol) drop-wise at (0 – 5 °C). The reaction mixture was stirred for (6 hrs.) and kept for two days at room temperature. Then reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice. The solid separated them dried and re-crystallized from ethanol **Scheme 2**.

Scheme [2]

Table (2): physical properties, yield and R_f of Azitiden 2-one [A₅-A₁₀]

Comp. No.	Ar	Molecular Formula/ g/mol	M.Wt	Color	M.P. (°C)	Yield (%)	R _f CHCl ₃
A ₁		C₁₄H₉N₄OCl 313		Dark yellow	250-252	70.2	0.66
A ₂		C₁₄H₁₂N₃O₂SCl 321		Light yellow	215-217	68.5	0.55
A ₃		C₁₃H₈N₃OCl₃ 328		orange	236-238	65.7	0.62
A ₄		C₁₄H₁₂N₃O₃Cl 305		brown	200-202	63.3	0.53
A ₅		C₁₆H₁₂N₃O₂Cl 313		Yellow	198-200	66	0.54

The Biological Activity ^[23] :

The bacteria species used are listed in tables (5). All strains were obtained from College of Education for Women, Tikrit University. They were grown up to the stationary phase nutrient bath at 37 °C and a sample of 0.5 ml of each bacteria was spread over a surface of a nutrient agar plate.

Antibacterial assay ^[24]:

Disc of filter paper (6 mm diameter) is sterilized at 140 °C for 1hr., and impregnated with the germs. DMSO was used as a solvent for

compounds (A₁, A₂, A₆, A₇, A₈, A₉, A₁₀). The same solvent was used for antibiotics (Amoxicillin, Ampicillin). Blank paper discs of DMSO was used as control. The inoculated plates are incubated at 37 °C for 24 hrs., the inhibition zone was measured. In all experiments the mean of each triplicate was measured.

Results and Discussion:

In this work many compounds were synthesized which includes schiff bases and azetidin-2-one as in the following Scheme3:

Scheme (3): synthesis of compounds [A1-A10].

Characterization of Schiff Bases [A₁-A₅] [25,26] :

In this work, 2-aminopyrimidine which on condensation with various selected aromatic aldehydes and in the presence of absolute ethanol and few drops of glacial acetic acid formed Schiff bases derivatives [A₁ – A₅]. The FT-IR spectra of Schiff Bases derivatives in general showed disappearance of (C=O) absorption of and appearances of (C=N) absorption band in (1640-1660) cm⁻¹, Further ¹H-NMR of compounds [A₃ and A₄] shown the presence of a singlet signal between δ (8.74 – 8.78) ppm indicating the formation of imine (HC=N) , and signal at δ (6.93 – 7.46) ppm shown the presence of aromatic protons for compounds [beside UV spectra, the transitions n-π* and π-π* have confirmed the presence of the un-bonded pair electrons on nitrogen, oxygen atoms and aromatic system (double bond). UV and IR and ¹HNMR absorbance spectra were given in table (3) and table (4) see fig (1)(3) (4)(7) and (8).

Characterization of Azetidin-2-one derivatives [A₆-A₁₀]^[22]

Azetidin-2-one derivatives (A₆-A₁₀) have synthesized from the reaction of compounds (A₁- A₅) with chloroacetyl chloride . The FT-IR spectra of Azetidin-2-one derivatives in general showed disappearance of (C=N) absorption band in (1622-1672) cm⁻¹ of schiff bases derivatives and appearances of (C-N) absorption band in (1244-1340) cm⁻¹ and appearances of (C=O) absorption band in (1666-1739) cm⁻¹, beside UV spectra, the transitions n-π* and π-π* have confirmed the presences of the un-bonded pairelectrons on nitrogen, oxygen atoms and aromatic system (double bond). UV and IR absorbance spectra were given in table (3) see fig (2) (5) and (6). ¹H-NMR spectrum of compound (A7 and A8) showed singlet signal at δ= (6.31) ppm due to C-H Azetidin ring, singlet signal at , multiple signal (7.50 - 7.90) ppm due to aromatic rings, spectrum is given in table (4) see fig (9) (10). In the study of ¹³CNMR spectroscopy of compound (A1,A6,A9), signs were observed and included in Table (5)) see fig(11)(12)and(13)

Table (3): FT-IR, UV/Vis. and ¹H-NMR data of the prepared compounds.

Comp. No.	Ar	λ_{max} λ_{max} EtOH	IR (KBr) cm ⁻¹					Others
			ν C=N) Sheiff	ν (C-H) Arom. Aliph.	ν (C=C) Arom.	ν (C=N) Pyi.	ν (C=O) Lactam	
A ₁		261 393	1640	3012 2947	1620	1581	-	, (CN)2274 ν
A ₂		248 398	1666	3041 2982	1626	1587	-	ν S-O,960 570 , ν CS
A ₃		217 342	1645	3059 2941	1606	1537	-	813 ν (C-Cl)
A ₄		218 390	1651	3090 2941	1583	1543	-	3607 ν (OH) (C-OCH ₃)Str. : 1356

A ₅		239 305	1653	3107 2964	1633	1593	-	-
A ₆		242 317	-----	3005 2958	1612	1579	1698	v (CN),2225 vC-N,1430,vC-Cl, 785,
A ₇		217 370	-----	3050 2922	1635	1591	1739	570v S=O,960 vC -S vC-N,1435,vC-Cl, 785
A ₈		261 393	-----	3007 2972	1614	1573	1730	vC-N,1435,vC-Cl, 866
A ₉		239 305	-----	3010 2956	1626	1548	1734	vC-N,1400,vC-Cl, 790 3437 v (OH) (C-OCH ₃)Str.1301
A ₁₀		216 320	-----	3051 2924	1610	1575	1666	vC-N,1413,vC-Cl, 790

Table(4): ¹H-NMR Data Compounds [A₃, A₄, A₇, and A₈].

Com p. No.	δ(C-H) Aromatic ppm m, nH	δ(N=CH) Imine ppm s, 1H	δ(CH=N) pyrimidin e ppm d, 2H	δ(CH=C) pyrimidin e ppm t, 1H	δ(N- CH) β- lactam ppm s, 1H	δ(HC- Cl) β-lactam ppm s, 1H	Others ppm
A ₃	(7.44-7.69)3H	8.66	8.33	6.68
A ₄	(7.44-7.68)4H	8.66	8.33	6.68	(s, 3H, N-CH ₃): δ3.34
A ₇	(7.58-7.93)4H	8.78	6.72	5.54	5.78	(s, 3H, S-CH ₃): δ1.21
A ₈	(7.58-7.93)3H	8.33	6.70	5.54	5.78

Table (5): ^{13}C -NMR Data Compounds [A₁, A₆, and A₉].

A₁	^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, δ 40.58 (DMSO- d_6 solvent) δ (=CH)171.53, δ (3CPyi.) 163.71, 153.38, 139.52, δ (6C _{ar}), 131.82, 128.02, 118.88, 117.37, δ (CN)112.67.
A₆	^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, δ 40.58 (DMSO- d_6 solvent) δ (3CPyi.) 158.97, 157.89, δ (C=156.66, 1 δ (6C _{ar}), 40.97, 129.59, 127.31, 118.56, 111.50, 111.33, δ (C-H _{Lactam}) 66.57, δ (Cl) 63.76
A₉	^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, δ 40.58 (DMSO- d_6 solvent) δ (C=O) 160.93, δ (3CPyi.) 158.17, 156.75, δ (6C _{ar}),148.24, 146.04, 127.82, 123.03, 115.50, 114.86, 111.50, δ (C-H _{Lactam})67.83, δ (C-Cl) 63.76, δ (CH ₃) 56.06.

Table (6): Elemental analysis of some of the prepared compounds.

Comp. No.	Molecular Formula	Found				Calculated			
		C%	H%	N%	O%	C%	H%	N%	O%
A ₁	C₁₂H₈N₄	69.22	3.87	26.91	69.10	3.82	26.80
A ₃	C₁₁H₇N₃Cl₂	52.41	2.80	16.67	50.44	2.90	16.70
A ₄	C₁₂H₁₁N₃OS	58.76	4.52	17.13	6.52	58.70	4.50	17.10	6.44
A ₆	C₁₄H₉N₄OCl	59.06	3.19	19.68	5.62	59.00	3.35	19.68	5.26
A ₇	C₁₄H₁₂N₃O₂SCI	52.26	3.76	13.06	9.94	52.32	3.60	13.12	9.90
A ₈	C₁₃H₈Cl₃N₃O	47.52	2.45	12.79	4.87	47.40	2.45	12.73	4.88
A ₉	C₁₃H₈Cl₃N₃O	55.00	3.96	13.75	15.70	54.87	4.00	13.20	15.60

Scheme (4): Mechanism [A₁-A₁₀].

Biological activity ^[23]:

The antimicrobial activity of the synthesized compounds [A₁, A₂, A₃, A₄, A₅, A₆, A₇, A₈, A₉, A₁₀] were examined by the agar diffusion method using four different bacterial species *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and

Staphylococcus Epidermidis. The results indicated that some of the assayed compounds showed a microbial activity against the used bacteria. Antibacterial activity of compounds [A₁, A₂, A₇, A₈] were given in fig (14) and (15). Evaluation of inhibitory activity of compounds prepared is given in fig (16-19).

Table (7): Antibacterial activity of some of the prepared compounds.

Comp. No.	Conc. mg/ml	<i>E. Coil</i>	<i>K. Pneumonia</i>	<i>S. Aureus</i>	<i>S. Epidermidis</i>	Inhibition distance
A ₁	25	+	++	-	-	0
	50	++	+++	+	+	1-2
	100	+++	+++	++	+	1-4
A ₂	25	+	++	+	+	1-2
	50	++	+++	++	+++	1-5
	100	+++	+++	+++	+++	4-5
A ₃	25	+	+	++	+	1-4
	50	+++	++	++	+++	2-5
	100	+++	+++	+++	+++	4-5
A ₄	25	+	+	-	++	0-2
	50	+++	++	+	+++	1-5
	100	+++	+++	++	+++	2-5
A ₅	25	-	-	-	-	0
	50	++	+	++	++	1-4
	100	++	++	++	++	2-4
A ₆	25	++	-	-	-	0
	50	++	+	+	++	1-4
	100	+++	+++	++	++	2-4
A ₇	25	-	-	-	+	2
	50	++	+	+	++	1-4
	100	+++	+	++	++	2-4
A ₈	25	-	-	-	-	0
	50	+	+	++	++	1-3
	100	+++	++	++	++	2-4
A ₉	25	-	-	-	-	0
	50	+	++	+	+	1-4
	100	++	++	++	++	2-4
A ₁₀	25	-	-	-	-	0
	50	+	+	+	+	1-2
	100	++	++	++	++	2-4

(-) = No inhibition

(+) = Inhibition zone (1-2) cm

(++) = Inhibition zone (2-4) cm

(+++)= Inhibition zone (4-5) cm

Table (8): Antibacterial efficacy of control treatments (antibiotics) in the growth of a number of negative and positive bacteria (diameter of the inhibition circuit measured by cm).

Comp. No.	Name	<i>E. Coil</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>S. Aureus</i>	<i>S. Epidermidis</i>
1	Amoxicillin	2.8	2.7	3.0	2.5
2	Ampicillin	3.7	2.5	2.5	2
3	Blank disk	0	0	0	0

Fig (1): UV/Vis spectrum of compound [A₃,A₄].

Fig (2): UV/Vis spectrum of compound [A₇,A₈].

Fig (5): FT-IR spectrum of compound [A₇].

Fig (6): FT-IR spectrum of compound [A₈].

Fig (7): ¹H-NMR spectrum of compound [A₃].

Fig (8): ¹H-NMR spectrum of compound [A₄].

Fig (9): ¹H-NMR spectrum of compound [A₇].

Fig (10): ¹H-NMR spectrum of compound [A₈].

Fig (11): ¹³C-NMR spectrum of compound [A₁].

Fig (12): ¹³CNMR spectrum of compound [A₆].

Fig (13): ¹³CNMR spectrum of compound [A₉].

Fig (14): Antibacterial activity of compounds [A₁, A₂] against *Escherichia coli*.

Fig (15): Antibacterial activity of compounds [A₆, A₇] against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Fig. (16): Evaluation of inhibitory activity of compounds prepared for *Escherichia coli*.

Fig. (17): Evaluation of inhibitory activity of compounds prepared for *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Fig. (18): Evaluation of inhibitory activity of compounds prepared for *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Fig. (19): Evaluation of inhibitory activity of compounds prepared for *Staphylococcus Epidermidis*.

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تحضير وتشخيص بعض مركبات 3-كلورو أزيثيديين-3-اون من المركب 2-امينو بيريميدين وتقييم فعاليتها البيولوجية

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تضمن هذا العمل تخليق بعض مشتقات 3-كلورو-أزيثيديين-2-اون ، على مرحلتين: الأولى تشمل مجموعة أمينية من 2-بيريميدين الأميني تم تكتيفها مع ألدهيدات عطرية مختلفة في وجود إيثانول مطلق لإعطاء مشتقات قواعد شيف الجديدة [A₁ – A₅] على التوالي. في الخطوة الثانية ، تم تفاعل مشتقات الإيمين الناتجة من [A₁ – A₅] مع كلورو أسيتيل كلوريد في وجود ثلاثي إيثيل أمين في 1-4-ديوكسان بواسطة تفاعل الطوق الحلقي فتم الحصول على 3-كلورو -1- (بيريميدين-أزيثيديين) 2 – اون [A₆ - A₁₀] على التوالي. شخصت باستخدام التقنيات الطيفية UV / Vis ، FT-IR ، C.H.N ، و ¹H-NMR و ¹³C-NMR لبعض المركبات المحضرة باستخدام DMSO-d⁶ كمذيب ، بالإضافة إلى درجة الانصهار وتحديد درجة نقاء TLC ، يتكون هذا العمل من دراسة النشاط البيولوجي لبعض المركبات المحضرة ضد أربعة أنواع من البكتيريا المسببة للأمراض مقاومة المضادات الحيوية ، المخدرات.